

A study of tribological behaviour of bio lubricants and their blends with GNP nanoparticles

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Abstract— The maximum amount of power produced in internal combustion engines is wasted in overcoming friction due to no. of moving components. In this regard, mineral lubricant oils, which are petroleum based and causing the environmental pollution, disposal of oil issues, and continuous utilization of these oils tend to cause depletion of crude oil resources. Hence, the current study focused on non-edible mahua oil mixed with commercial lubricant oil and non-metallic carbon-based Graphene Nanoplatelets (GNPs) as a bio raw oil-lubricant-nano sample to evaluate the physiochemical and tribological properties of an aluminium pin on a high carbon steel disc wear testing machine under different loading (20, 35, and 50N) and at a fixed speed (900 rpm) and radial distance (3000 m). A 10% vol. of raw oil is blended with 90% vol. of 10W30 commercial oil and termed as B10. The GNP nanoparticles (NPs) are included in B10 at a dosage of 0.25, 0.5 and 0.75 mg/l and referred as B10+0.25%, B10+0.5%, and B10+0.75%. The results showed that the nano assisted blends are found to be stable and their physio-chemical characteristics are found to be on par with American Society for Testing and Materials (ASTM) standards. The Coefficient of Friction (COF), Wear rate, Wear loss, and Frictional force are lowered by 13.10, 55.1, 80, and 11.1% for B10+0.25% sample as compared to 10W30 sample at higher loads which shows the potentiality of NPs as a sustainable additive for Mahua bio-lubricant oils in enhancing their performance on pin on disc wear testing machine.

KEYWORDS— RAW OIL, LUBRICANT OIL, TRIBOLOGICAL PROPERTIES, WEAR RATE, COEFFICIENT OF FRICTION

I. INTRODUCTION

Tribology is the study of friction, wear, and lubrication its plays a crucial role in the performance and longevity of mechanical systems, particularly in automotive engines. It integrates principles from physics, chemistry, materials science, and engineering to understand and control surface interactions between moving components. In recent days tribology is very crucial in various industries such as automotive, aerospace, manufacturing, and biomedical engineering, where minimizing friction and wear is essential for efficiency and longevity [1]. Lubrication helps to reduce the friction by applying a lubricant to contact points of metal surfaces. Its key functions are (i) forming a protective lubricant film between metals during contact, (ii) reducing heat generation, and (iii) removing metal debris. However, the disposal of used mineral oils contributes to environmental pollution, which must be managed. Due to human negligence, oil spills on land and, more critically, in aquatic environments remain a significant concern [2]. Every working surface is rough, and this roughness creates macroscopic ridges and valleys that contribute to friction. Tribological interactions between exposed surfaces, the interfacing material, and the surrounding system can lead to material loss. This material loss due to abrasion is known as wear. Wear occurs when the surfaces of engineering components are subjected to rolling or sliding motion under load [3]. The type of friction generated in these motions depends on the load and the geometry of the surfaces. Wear can be reduced by modifying the surface properties of solids through “surface engineering” processes or by using lubricants [4]. Lubricating the moving parts has been known to humans since the invention of the wheel. At that time the primary aim of using a lubricant was to reduce the friction, it can be easily visualized that the use of wooden axles and wheels, or even a combination of metallic wheels and axles would create great amount of friction and wear. Lubrication then becomes the basic need for mechanical machines [5]. Lubricants function as an anti-friction material, casing smoother work, reducing the risks of commonly encountered undesirable failures and preserving authentic machine operations. Lubricants are important to machinery in general for lubrication, heat transfer, power transmission and protection against corrosion. Lubricants are a base oils, additives for the advantages of improved properties. A main characteristic of lubricant oil is its viscosity, since this prevents contact between the surfaces. Some essential elements used in choosing a lubricant include consistency, hardness, chemical stability, corrosivity,

flammability, environmental effects, availability, temperature stability and price [6]. Lubricants acts as lifeguards of any tribo-system for wide range of utilities and applications. In general lubricants are the multifaceted agents required for smoother tribo-pair operations. Depending upon the properties required, availability, technology, and compatibility, it was oscillated from the nature based to conventional mineral based through the ages [7,8]. In industrial machines, friction and wear lead to energy loss and material waste which necessitating the proper control. The mechanical components in relative motion and come into contact thereby, friction arises, dissipating energy and reducing the efficiency of mechanical devices [9]. Several studies have been conducted to analyze the renewable energy resources available in India. Increased energy demands from different sectors and the impending depletion of fossil-based reserves, and increasing oil prices have forced the Indian government to take relevant measures to consider alternative approaches. On other side, the commercial lubricant oils (Synthetic oils) have major drawbacks including not biodegradable, additives separation, sludge formation which causes clogging the filters, seal compatibility issues, and high cost [10,11]. This study was carried out to address some of the research gaps in the development of alternative energy sources. In this regard, Bio-lubricants have emerged as a promising alternative, offering greater sustainability and being more environmentally friendly [12]. In recent years, with increased petroleum costs, decreased petroleum reserves, and environmental concerns as major factors, vegetable oils as lubricating agents are making a slow but steady comeback. They exhibit superior biodegradability compared to conventional synthetic oils, making them a safer option [13]. The use of vegetable oil may enhance drought in human daily food resources. Therefore, many studies are focusing on non-edible oils to employ in lubrication fields. In the current study, raw mahua oil is considered as a supplementary lubricant oil based on its properties which are close to lubricant oil [14]. However, despite their ecological benefits, bio-lubricants still lack some of the advanced performance characteristics found in traditional lubricants. The major issue of vegetable oils is that they create solid gel at low temperatures which clogs the oil filters and engine components [15]. Hence, the recent research studies suggests that the limited amount of vegetable oil can be mixed with commercial lubricating oils. By combining raw oil with suitable additives, customized lubricant formulations can be developed to meet the demands of various industrial and automotive applications, ensuring improved efficiency and longevity of engine components [16]. Moreover, blending raw oil-commercial lubricant oil blends with NPs addition enhances its performance, improving viscosity, oxidation stability, and anti-wear properties. Additives such as anti-friction agents, detergents, and dispersants help maintain engine cleanliness, extend oil life, and optimize lubrication [17,18]. NPs as antiwear and friction-reducing agent are successfully applied in the field of tribology to reduce friction and wear, which is conducive to energy conservation and emission reduction [19,20]. Over the past few decades, numerous studies have highlighted that incorporating NPs such as metals, metal oxides, metal sulfides, carbonates, carbon-based materials, organic compounds, and rare-earth compounds in to lubricants effectively reduces both friction and wear.

A. Novelty of the current Study

Based on the literature survey, Bio based lubricants derived from non-edible oils with commercial lubricant oil offer good lubricity, higher viscosity index, higher flash point, and good anti wear properties as compared with conventional lubricants. The NPs addition in bio lubricants or bio-commercial based lubricant oil blends further enhances

the tribo behaviour of oils. The enhancement in friction-reducing and anti-wear properties is attributed to the unique characteristics of the NPs, including their size, shape, physico-chemical, and thermal properties. No research is found with the addition of carbon based NPs such as GNPs in raw oil (mahua oil based)-commercial lubricant blends to improve the physio-chemical and tribological properties. Hence, this current study focuses on improving the tribological properties of raw oil-commercial lubricant oil blends with NPs dispersion.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

An *Madhuca longifolia* is commonly known as madhuka, mahura, madkam, mahuwa, Butter tree, mahura, mahwa, mohulo, Iluppai, Mee or Ippa-chettu [21]. It is a fast-growing tree that grows to approximately 20 meters in height, possesses evergreen or semi-evergreen foliage, and belongs to the family Sapotaceae. It is adaptable to arid environments, being a prominent tree in tropical mixed deciduous forests in India in the states of Maharashtra, Odisha, Chhattisgarh, Jharkhand, Uttar Pradesh, Bihar, Andhra Pradesh, Madhya Pradesh, Kerala, Gujarat, West Bengal and Tamil Nadu.

It is one of the forest based tree-borne non-edible oils with huge production potential of around 60 million tons per year in India. The gestation period is 4-7 years and produces edible fruits containing 1-2 kidney shaped kernels. Apart from the oil yielding capacities, the plant's fruit has medicinal use in ulcers, rheumatism, itches; its flower can be used as animal fodder after fermentation. Its cake can be used as fertilizers, bio pesticides, as animal fodder and as dye removal from waste water. More importantly, the plant has carbon negative role as it fix Carbon dioxide (CO₂) around 639 kg/tree. Furthermore, the plantation is promoted on around 62,463 ha of land across India. The kernel of the Mahua indica fruit contains approximately 50% oil. The free fatty acid content in the mahua oil is shown in Table 1. The solvent n-hexane (99%), SPAN80 and GNPs NPs are provided by Platonic Nanotech pvt. Ltd, Jharkhand, India.

TABLE 1
PRESENTS THE FREE FATTY ACIDS OF MAHUA OIL

Fatty acids	percentage
Palmatic(c16:0)	19.2
Stearic(c18:0)	23.4
Oleic(c18:1)	58.6
Linoliec(c18:2)	12.4
Arachidic(c20:0)	2.1

B. Extraction of raw mahua oil

Mahua seeds are collected from maredumilli forest, Andhra Pradesh, India. Once the seeds are separated from their kernels, they are sun-dried to reduce moisture content which is essential for efficient oil extraction. After drying, oil was extracted using mechanical press (cold or hot pressing). In cold pressing, seeds are pressed at low temperatures to retain maximum nutrients, though the yield is relatively low. In hot pressing, the seeds are slightly heated before pressing, which increases oil yield but may alter some properties. Once the oil is extracted, it undergoes filtration to remove impurities. The final purified Mahua oil is stored in airtight containers, away from heat and light, to maintain its stability and extend its shelf life. Mahua oil is widely used in biofuels, cosmetics, soap-making, and medicinal applications due to its beneficial properties. The flow chart of current study is shown in the Fig. 1.

Figure 1. Presents the flow chart of methodology

C. Sample preparation for the test

Raw Mahua oil blended with commercial lubricant oil (10W30) at a ratio of 10 to 90 Vol. % which is termed as B10. In the next samples, the GNP NPs (0.25, 0.5, and 0.75 mg/l) were dispersed with non-ionic Lipophilic QPAN80 surfactant with a concentration of 1:4 (GNPs : QPAN80) in the presence of n-hexane [22,23]. After mixing, n-hexane is evaporated and the surface modified GNPs at a dosage of 0.25, 0.5, and 0.75 mg/l dispersed in B10 (10% of Raw mahua oil in 90% of 10W30 lubricant oil) blend to enhance the stability using a water bath and probe sonicator (Hielscher -ltrasonic UP400S, 160 W, and 40 kHz) at a frequency of 40 kHz for half an hour which is named as B10+0.25%, B10+0.5%, B10+0.75%. The samples Lubricant oil, Raw Mahua Oil, B10, NPs (at a dosage of 0.25, 0.50, and 0.75 ppm) including in bio-lubricant blends are tested on Pin on Disc Wear Testing Machine (NOVUS TRIBO SOLUTIONS MAKE) on a standard testing parameters of 900 rpm, radial distance of 3000 m, under different loads 20, 35, and 50 N [24]. The proposed lubricant sample's test matrix is mentioned in Table 2. The preparation of oil samples with NPs are shown in Fig. 2.

TABLE 2
PROPOSED TEST MATRIX AND TEST CONDITIONS

Sl. No.	Prepared Samples	NP- Dosage (mg/l)	Raw Oil (ml)	Lub oil (ml)
1	Lubricant Oil	-	-	1000
2	Raw Mahua Oil	-	1000	-
3	B10	-	100	900
4	B10+0.25 mg/l	0.25	100	900
5	B10+0.50 mg/l	0.5	100	900
6	B10+0.75 mg/l	0.75	100	900

Figure 2. Presents the preparation of oil samples a) ultrasonication of nano lubricant blends, b) Raw mahua oil, and lubricant oil (10W30), and c) Prepared samples.

D. Characterization of GNPs

The images acquired from the field emission scanning electron microscope (FE-SEM) are shown in Fig. 3(a). The picture demonstrates surface topography and composition of the sample in which the presence of GNPs as well as the expansion of the lattice plane are observed [22]. An High-Resolution Transmission Electron Microscopy (HRTEM) (MODEL: JEOL-JEM2100F) was used to acquire a higher magnification image of the GNPs sample for a closer investigation as shown in Fig 3(b). It analyzes the morphology of GNPs nano additives [23]. The higher magnification image shows that GNPs are made up of around five layers of graphene and have a thickness of about 6 nm, as described by the manufacturer in Table 3.

TABLE 3
ILLUSTRATES THE PROPERTIES OF GNPS

Item	Description
Item Description Supplier	Platonic Nanotech pvt. Ltd.
Average size of nanoplatelets	5–10 nm thickness, length 5 μm
Thermal conductivity	2000 watts/m-k
Mechanical tensile modulus	>1000 Gpa
Surface area (SSA)	200–240 m^2/g
Density	2.5 g/cm^3
Purity	>99%
Appearance	Black

Fig. 3 (a) FE -SEM Images of GNPs nanoplatelets at magnification level of 110000x (b) HR- TEM Image of GNPs at 20nm
E. *Materials of Pin on Disc Apparatus*

Aluminium, a low-density material, exhibits excellent corrosion resistance due to surface passivation. It is also known for being relatively soft, durable, lightweight, ductile, and malleable [25]. Aluminium was chosen as the piston material, which experiences the highest friction, with a hardness of 98 HRB. Additionally, it offers resistance to both wear and corrosion. For the disc, high carbon steel was selected due to its superior hardness (65 HRC) and wear resistance. The pin was machined into a cylindrical shape using a lathe, with one end flattened to ensure proper contact with the disc. It had a diameter of 6 mm and a length of 30 mm. To prepare the pin for the experiment, it was polished using emery paper with grit sizes of 200, 400, 600, and 1200 nm.

F. *Test Set Up*

The lubricity of a fluid is a crucial property that affects the friction and wear behavior of contacting surfaces. In addition to evaluate the lubricant performance, the pin-on-disc tribometer is utilized to study tribological behavior of prepared samples with the ASTM G99 standard [26]. The pin on disc test rig is shown in Figure 4. The schematic lay out of test setup is depicted in Figure 5.

For all test conditions, the sliding speed (900 rpm) and sliding distance (3000 m) were kept constant. During testing, 50 ml of lubricant was supplied in accordance with the specified test conditions. After each test, the pins were removed from the apparatus, cleaned with acetone, and then dried using tissue paper to absorb any remaining lubricant,

which was later used for further surface analysis. The loads (20, 35, and 50 N) were manually applied, and the lubricants were applied on the wear disc at a constant rate to ensure full coverage at the contact point between the aluminium pin and the high-carbon steel wear disc. The tests carried out for the prepared oil samples under various conditions to evaluate coefficient of friction, wear rate, frictional force, and wear loss. The tests are conducted for 4 times to get the average values and reproducibility. The test parameters under controlled conditions are mentioned in the Table 4. Wear scar imaging was conducted using a Metzer optical microscope, with the average scar image determined from data collected over three observations. To calculate the material's wear rate, the pin's weight was measured using a precision balance machine before and after testing. Prior to weighing, the pin was cleaned with acetone to ensure accurate examination.

TABLE 4
THE TEST PARAMETERS DURINT THE EXPERIMENT

Sl. No.	Parameter	Value
1	Load (N)	20,35,50
2	Sliding speed (rpm)	900
3	Sliding distance (m)	3000
4	Time (sec)	600
5	Track diameter (mm)	54

Fig. 4. Shows the experimental setup of Pin on Disc.

Fig. 5 Schematic lay out of Pin on disc Wear testing Apparatus.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

A. Physiological properties

The kinematic viscosity was measured using a standardized saybolt viscometer according to the ASTM D-445 and the formula used is given in Eq. 1 [27]. The flash point and fire point of the oil were determined using the Cleveland Open Cup Apparatus, following the ASTM D-92 standard [1]. The oil density was determined using a hydrometer standardized as per ASTM D5002, under atmospheric pressure and room temperature. Viscosity Index is measured for the all prepared samples using Redwood Viscometer, following ASTM D 2270 standard and the formula to find the Viscosity Index is given in Eq. 2 [28]. The tribological properties are measured at Metro Composite Testing lab, Chennai, India. The Physio-chemical properties results for raw lubricant, raw mahua oil, and raw bio-lubricant with NPs are presented in the Table 5.

$$\text{Viscosity} = At - \frac{B}{t} \quad \text{Eq. (1)}$$

Where, A = 0.264, and B = 190 when t = 40 to 85 Sec

A = 0.247, and B = 65 when, t = 85-2000 Sec

$$\text{Viscosity Index} = \frac{L-H}{L-U} \times 100 \quad \text{Eq. (2)}$$

Where, L = Kinematic Viscosity of Commercial Lubricating oil at 40°C,

H = Kinematic Viscosity of a Reference Commercial Lubricating oil at 40 °C,

U = Kinematic Viscosity of Prepared Same at 40 °C.

TABLE 5
PRESENTS THE PHYSIO-CHEMICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF TESTED LUBRICANT SAMPLES WITH NANO ADDITIONS.

Properties/Tested Samples	ASTM Standard with limits	Raw Lubricant Oil	Raw Mahua Oil	B10	B10+0.25%	B10+0.5%	B10+0.75%
Density at 15-35° (g/ml)	D5002 (0.75-0.95)	0.886	0.900	0.892	0.900	0.906	0.910
Kinematic Viscosity (mm ² /sec)	D445 (10-100 Cst at 40°C)	74.76	42.76	78.19	80.34	82.48	84.46
	D445 (2-25 Cst at 100°C)	10.99	8.2	12.46	14.2	15.4	16.5
Flash Point @ °C	D92 (>200)	190	241	215	210	202	198
Fire Point @ °C	D92	195	244	214	215	208	204
Viscosity Index	D2270 (90-110)	95	180	105	110	114	120

B. Tribological Properties

1. Coefficient of Friction (COF) Analysis:

The COF plays vital role in reducing friction with reference to the tested period of each sample which minimizes the wear and tear rate of metal components and improves the life of the engine. Further, it reduces the noise, and absorbs heat from the engine components. The COF vs. Time for the tested lubricant oil samples under various loads (20, 35, and 50 N) are depicted in Fig. 6a, b, and c. It is observed from the Fig. 6a. that the COF results are found to be increased (0.2625, 0.3620, and 0.3310) for dry condition (with no lubrication condition) as the load increases when correlated to other samples. Further, the samples raw mahua oil and commercial lubricant oil (10W30 commonly used for 2-wheel vehicles) showed reduced COF values such as 0.17 approximately due to the similar density, and viscosity properties. Moreover, the sample B10 results in reduced COF values 0.1362, 0.1112, 0.1351 at different load conditions 20, 35, and 50 N respectively as depicted in 6a,b, and c. Nevertheless, the NPs dispersed B10 samples at a dosage of (0.25, 0.50, and 0.75 mg/l) results in reduced COF 0.05 to 0.15 with reference to the running time. The decreased COF values are found to be 0.1263, 0.1254, and 0.1200 for B10+0.75 , B10+0.5, and B10+0.25 samples respectively at 600 sec running time of the pin on the disc to cover 3000 m at full load condition (50N) as shown in Fig. 6c. The maximum COF is lowered by 63.74, and 13.10% for B10+0.25 sample when compared to Dry condition and commercial lubricant 10W30 sample. The reduced COF is due to the improved viscosity, density, and Viscosity Index at less concentration of NPs while, the higher dosage of NPs tend to agglomeration, sedimentation, and reduced stability. Further, the decreased values are owing to the enhanced stability, enhanced surface area, provided better lubricity due to well dispersion of NPs with sufficient thickness of lubricant film, and reduced wear. Moreover, the NPs are filled in the fine gaps in the surface of the disc which leads to provide smooth surface and proper lubricity. This phenomenon tend to cause rolling mechanism instead of sliding friction [1]. Thus,

reducing the wear on the disc surface with the aid of nano dispersion in the B10 sample. The results are well correlated with the similar studies [28,29].

Fig. 6. Illustrates the Coefficient of Friction vs. Time for the tested lubricant samples at different loads a) 20 N, b) 30 N, and c) 50 N

2. Wear rate Analysis:

The wear rate is the rate at which material is lost from the surface of a disc when the pin glide against the disc under an applied load due to friction. The wear rate for the tested lubricant oil samples for a running time of 600 sec and 3000 m radial distance at different loads (20, 35, and 50 N) are illustrated in Fig. 7a, b, and c. It is noticed from the Fig. 7. that the wear rate is tremendously high (76, 160, and 640 microns) for dry condition at all loads when compared to other samples. Moreover, the raw mahua oil posses higher wear (69, 100, and 335 microns) as correlated to commercial lubricant oil sample (52, 65, and 290 microns) at different load conditions. Further, the GNP NPs dispersed bio-lubricant B10 blends reduced wear to a maximum extent (16, 30, and 130 microns) at 20, 35, and 50 N loads for B10+0.25% bio-lubricant sample. The wear rate is greatly reduced by 78.9, 81.2, and 79.6% for B10+0.25% sample when compared to dry condition at 20, 35, and 50 N loads. Similarly, the wear rate is well decreased by 69.2, 53.8, and 55.1% for B10+0.25% blend as compared to commercial lubricant oil sample without dispersion of nano additives at 20, 35, and 50 N loads. The reduction in wear rate is owing to anti-wear properties of the prepared lubricant oil sample with GNP nano additives. The wear rate decreases due to improved stability, and homogeneity of GNPs in base lubricant oil. Further, the GNP included bio-lubricant sample at low dosage reduced the wear rate due to the adsorption on the surface to promote anti wear property, and the ability of NPs to disperse in base oil sample without sedimentation at low concentration [14]. While, the higher dosage of NPs in base oils leading to create

improper adhesive bonding between the NPs and base oils and repulsive force between the NPs which tend to agglomeration and sedimentation, and poor adsorption of oil sample on the disc surface. Similar findings are observed in the literature [1,30].

Fig. 7. Illustrates the Wear Rate vs. Time for the tested lubricant samples at different loads a) 20 N, b) 30 N, and c) 50 N.

3. Wear loss Analysis:

In a pin-on-disc apparatus, wear loss relates to the quantity of material (pin or disc) removed throughout the test due to sliding wear, which is commonly measured as a change in weight or volume and it is critical for determining material wear resistance. The wear loss vs loads of the worn disc for all tested samples including Dry condition, 10W30, raw mahua oil, B10 (bio raw oil-lubricant), and B10 with GNP nano additives at a dosage of 0.25, 0.5, 0.75% are depicted in Fig. 8. It is clear from the figure that the wear loss is found to be maximum (0.06, 0.07, and 0.17g) for dry condition since there is no lubricant oil between the surfaces. While, the raw mahua oil reduced the wear to 0.05, 0.04, and 0.08g which is due to high viscosity of the oil sample as compared to the dry condition at three different loads. Whereas, the commercial lubricant further reduced the wear loss to 0.04, 0.03, and 0.05g at different loads. Further, the B10 sample reduced the wear loss compared to the above three samples which is owing to improved physio-chemical properties of the sample. Moreover, the nano assisted B10 sample reduced wear rate greatly to 0.01 at all loads for B10+0.25% sample. The maximum reduction in wear rate is about 94.1, and 80% for B10+0.25% sample as correlated to dry condition, and 10W30 sample at full load condition. The decreased wear loss is due to rolling effect of NPs in the sample, anti-wear properties of nano assisted-bio-commercial lubricant blends, and the sample B10+0.25% is found to be potential and sustainable nano assisted bio-lubricant sample [14]. Similar observations are seen in a study [1,30].

Fig.8. Wear loss vs Loads for the tested samples.

4. Friction force Analysis:

In the pin-on-disc apparatus, frictional force is the force that resists the relative motion between the pin and the rotating disc surface in contact. This force is caused by the interaction of the two surfaces and is influenced by several factors such as materials, normal load, speed, and lubrication. The frictional force vs load for various lubricant samples are illustrated in Fig. 9. It is clear from the graph that the frictional force is increased as the load increases and the frictional force is found to be more for dry condition (5, 13, and 16.5N) as correlated to other samples. Further, frictional force is gradually decreasing for the raw mahua oil, 10W30, and B10 sample due the increasing viscosity and lubricity property. While, the GNPs dispersed B10 sample reduced the frictional force to 2, 2.75, and 6N for B10+0.25% sample respectively at higher load. The frictional force is decreased by 60, 78.8, and 63.6% for B10+0.25% sample as correlated to the dry condition. While, the frictional force is lowered by 29.3, 31, and 11.1% for the same sample (B10+0.25%) as compared to the commercial lubricant. The highest percentage of reduction is found to be 33.3 for B10+0.25% sample when compared to the 10W30 oil. This reduction is achieved due to the synergistic values of bio-lubricant and NPs. The bio-lubricant sample, and nano included bio-lubricant sample enhances the lubrication properties and NPs are well filled on the fine gaps of the disc surface which causing the rolling mechanism and reduced frictional force. Hence, the B10+0.25% oil sample is proved to be more sustainable, eco-friendly, and act as a high performance lubricant oil [31].

Fig. 9. Friction Force vs Load for the tested samples

5. Worn surface analysis:

Worn surface analysis is the study of the surface damage and material loss that occurs due to wear during mechanical contact. It is commonly performed in tribology (the study of friction, wear, and lubrication) to understand the wear mechanisms and improve material performance. The Metzer optical microscope is used to capture the worn surface of the pin material as shown in the Fig. 10. As it is evidenced that the worn surface of the pin material contain many grooves which are cut in depth due to lack of lubricant film between the pin and the disc surface as seen in Fig. 10a. Further, the microscopic image Fig 10b. represents the worn surface of the pin for 10W30 oil sample which indicates the reduced deep grooves, and noticed with no. of pit holes. Whereas, the addition of GNPs at a dosage of 0.25 mg/l in B10 sample reduced the coefficient of friction, wear rate, wear loss, and friction force. Thereby, the Fig. 10c shows the minimum range of grooves and with no pit holes. The reduced grooves, and pit holes are attributed to the improved stability of NPs in base oil sample, enhanced viscosity, and rolling action of NPs in the gaps between the pin and disc surface [14,32]. While, at excessive concentration of NPs tend to agglomeration, and improved wear and friction. The similar images are seen the research articles [33,34].

Fig. 10. Metzer microscopic images of pin in Wear test a) Dry condition b) Commercial lubricant oil (10W30), and c) B10+0.25% sample.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The current study focuses on increasing the tribological properties of raw oil-commercial lubricant oil blends with GNPs NPs dispersion. The coefficient of friction, wear rate, wear loss, and wear scar image are important parameters in evaluating the tribological properties of lubricant oil which enhances the performance of the engine as well as improving the life of the engine. The samples prepared are Raw Mahua oil, commercial lubricant oil 10W30, B10, GNPs addition (0.25, 0.50, 0.75%) in B10 sample and tested for physio-chemical and tribological properties on pin on disc apparatus. The results are compared with dry condition with no lubricant oil and commercial lubricant oil as a standard reference. The following inferences are prepared from the above results and discussions:

- The nano assisted lubricant oil samples are found to be stable at low concentration which are evidenced by FESEM and HRTEM and the physio-chemical properties of prepared samples are observed to be with in the ASTM standards.
- The COF is found to be decreased by 63.74, and 13.10% for B10+0.25% sample as compared to dry condition and 10W30 sample at full load which is due to stability of GNPs in B10, improved viscosity, and nano lubricant film formation between the worn surfaces.
- Wear rate increases with increase in load but, wear rate is found to be lowered by 71.6, and 13.10% for B10+0.25% blend as correlated to the dry condition and 10W30 sample. As the NPs concentration increases, the samples tend to agglomerate and sedimentation after 24 hours which causes stability issues.
- Moreover, the wear loss due to friction is decreased for GNPs dispersed B10 sample at lower dosage. The maximum reduction in wear loss is found to be 94.1, and 80% when compared to dry condition and 10W30 sample at higher loads which is owing to rolling mechanism and improved viscosity index.
- Further, the friction force is also evidenced to decrease by 63.6, and 11.1% for the same sample as compared to dry condition and commercial lubricant oil sample which is because of conversion of roller friction instead of sliding friction.
- Nevertheless, the wear scar image of a pin on dry condition is found with high intensified deep blurs, whereas, commercial lubricant oil represents the reduced blur marginally but, pit holes are found. While, the sample B10+0.25% shows with less blurs, and no pit holes which refers to the decreased wear rate, wear loss, and COF.
- The results are compared with dry condition, and commercial lubricant oil. The nano included B10 sample with low concentration is found to be potential and more sustainable in improving tribological performance of the pin on disc apparatus and suggest to use in internal combustion engine operation.

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